

STUDIES ON THE PHYSICO-CHEMICAL PARAMETERS OF SEEDS AND SEED OILS OF WHITE STAR APPLE AND PAW-PAW.

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ABSTRACT

Chrysophyllum albidum Linn (White star apple, WSA) and *Carica papaya* Linn (Paw-paw, PP) seeds and their oils are uncommon sources of resources either for domestic or industrial uses. The seeds of these commonly consumed fruits were analysed and were found to respectively (WSA and PP) show moisture content as 3.8% and 84.41%, total ash content: 2.8% and 8.2%, Water Soluble ash 1.2% and 4.2% , Alkalinity of soluble ash: 0.0003mol/dm³ and 0.0004mol/dm³ , Acid-insoluble ash 2.3% and 3.5%. Their oils are rarely applied, probably because of their under exploitation. Their oil yields were low: 4% for WSA and 30%, for PP. Other parameters studied for the rare oils are pH, specific gravity, melting and boiling point, refractive index, acid value, peroxide value, iodine value, saponification value and Carotenoid content. The values of these parameters showed these oils to be valuable raw materials for domestic or industrial applications.

KEYWORDS: Characterization, *Chrysophyllum albidum*, *Carica papaya*, oil extraction.

INTRODUCTION

There is a short fall of edible oils and fats in Nigeria. This is due to the increasing population (140,000,000) and the rising industrialization of Nigeria's economy. Total vegetable oil production in Nigeria in 1984 was estimated between 160,000-175,000MT and Nigeria's total consumption of vegetable oil in the same year stood at 948,000MT and this was when Nigeria's population was barely a 100 million. As then, a shortfall existed and was being largely met by increased imports of oils from other countries which put a heavy drain on Nigeria's foreign exchange earnings (Osagie *et al.*, 1986). Presently this position has worsened with current Nigeria's population and infrastructural and agricultural down turn.

The extraction and use of vegetable oil has for centuries played an important role in the manufacture of a large number of industrial products and food items. Low cost oil seed crops are needed to produce inexpensive oils suitable for food, pharmaceutical, beauty products and industrial applications. Some of such possible alternative crops are White star apple and paw-paw. Besides, Nigeria with a population of about 160 million as a nation runs at an oil deficit of between 300-400 MT, having had an annual production 1.4 million MT of palm oil as at 2014. This deficit need be bridged.

Fruits contain seeds and seeds are generally known to harbour oils at different percentages. Seeds are composed of varying amount of edible, non-edible and fibrous materials. They are also repositories of various organic and inorganic substances which are active and non-active physiologically. Oil is one of the physiological active components of seeds and they have found wide application in life. Oil is defined as any neutral, non-polar chemical substance that is a viscous liquid at ambient temperature. It is both hydrophobic (immiscible with water literally 'water fearing') and lipophilic (miscible with oils, literally 'fat loving'), oils have a

high carbon and hydrogen content. The general definition oil includes classes of chemical compounds that may be otherwise related in structure, properties and uses.

Oils may be animal, vegetable or petrochemical in origin. Vegetable fats and vegetable oils are substances derived from plants that are composed of triglycerides. Normally, oils are liquid at room temperature, and fats are solid; a dense brittle fat is called a wax. Physically oils and fats are basically similar in composition. The difference between oil and a fat is that oil is usually liquid at ambient temperature such as olive oil while a fat is solid (Hamed, 2006). Also vegetable oils consist primarily of triglycerides and they are insoluble in water and greasy to touch. Vegetable oils also consist of triglycerides between 95 and 99%. They may also contain soluble vitamins (A, D, E and K), phytosterols, natural pigments and phospholipids from 1 to 5% (Evrard *et al.*, 2007).

Oils find wide and varied applications in life, in the industry, at home, in pharmaceuticals and in socials in diet, they play an essential role, they ensure nutritional function, they contribute to the energy supply and they are sources of essential fatty acids. They have also found uses as preservatives, as some have been found to possess unique bactericidal properties beside the common characteristic of being able to occlude oxygen from its presence (Ugbogu and Akukwe, 2009). There is the need therefore to increase the variety of the oils available to man by prospecting for oil in unconventional sources, such as *Chrysophyllum albidum* and *Carica papaya* Linn seeds. These seeds are usually discarded when these fruits are eaten and hence of no economic value.

***Chrysophyllum albidum* Linn**

Chrysophyllum albidum, also known as White Star apple is a native of many parts of tropical Africa. In Nigeria, it is found in urban and rural centers in the months of December to April. It is an ever green tree that belongs to the family of sapotaceae which has up to 800 species, it grows up to 25-40 meters in height having a mature girth varying from 1.5 to 2.0 meters (Orwa *et al.*, 2009). The fruit is almost spherical, with a slightly pointed tip by greenish grey when immature, turning orange-red or brownish to golden yellow sometimes with speckles when ripe. The pulp may be orange, pinkish, or light yellow in colour, containing 3 to 5 seeds which are not usually eaten. The seeds are shiny when ripe, dark brown to blackish in colour, obliquely ellipsoid to obvoid in shape, about 2.8cm in length and 1.2cm in width. They are compressed in the pulp with one sharp edge and a star shaped arrangement of the seeds they are hard and when broken reveals a milk coloured cotyledon (Emmanuel and Francis, 2010). The fruit was found to have the highest content of ascorbic acid per 100g of edible fruit, which is about 100 times that of oranges and 10 times of that of guava and cashew. It is also an excellent source of vitamins, iron and flavours to diets. The fruits also contain 90% anacardic acid, which is used industrially in protecting wood and a source of resin.

***Carica papaya* Linn.**

According to research, *Carica papaya* is originated from tropical and subtropical America. It belongs to the family Caricaceae from *Carica* genus. The plant is recognised by its weak and usually unbranched soft stem yielding copious white latex and crowded by a terminal cluster of large and long stalked leaves, is rapidly growing and can grow up to 20m tall

Carica papaya contains many biologically active compounds. Two important compounds are chymopapain and papain which are widely known as being useful for digestive disorders and disturbances of the gastrointestinal tract. The fruit is oval to practically round, sometimes pear shaped or elongated club-shaped or cylindrical and weighs up to 9 kg. The flesh is yellow-orange, soft, and juicy. The central cavity contains large quantities of seeds that comprise about 15% of the wet weight of the fruit (Desai, 1995).

Ripe papaya typically is consumed fresh for dessert, in fruit salad or used as processed products by humans for their flavour and nutritional value. Its consumption has been attributed to aid digestion. Unripe fruit is consumed cooked similarly to a vegetable or used in salad, especially in South East Asia. Papaya is regarded as a good source of riboflavin and carotene, an excellent source of ascorbic acid and a considerable source of calcium, iron, thiamin, pantothenic, niacin and vitamin K (Chan, 2008). This present study seeks to examine the physico-chemical properties of seeds and rare seed oils from the white star apple and paw -paw in order to expand its utility to maximum.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

MATERIALS

Sample Collection and Preparation

The *Chrysophyllum albidum* and *Carica papaya* fruits were obtained at Auchi market in Estako west local government area of Edo state. The seeds of the white star apple were separated manually from the fruits, cleaned free of foreign matter and dried for 3 to 4 days in the sun at ambient temperature for easy removal of their shells. After deshelling, the pulps were further sundried for a period of one week to reduce the moisture content. A manual grinding machine (coroner Tim) was used to crush the dried cotyledon to a powdery form to increase the surface area for oil extraction.

The pawpaw fruit was divided into two halves with a knife and the seeds were scooped out with a spoon, washed with distilled water to remove all the fruit flesh, the epicarp was removed and the seeds were dried under the sun for five days. The seeds were then pulverized with the aid of a blending machine. All reagents were of analytical grade unless otherwise stated. The physicochemical analyses were carried out in triplicates unless otherwise stated.

METHODS

Oil extraction and Characterization

The powdered seeds were extracted in 400g portions for 6-8hrs with n-hexane in a soxhlet extractor. The oil was recovered from the solvent by simple distillation. The oil was then placed in a water bath at 60^{0c} for 30minutes to remove the residual solvent. It was observed that more oil was extracted at 40-60^{0c} than at 60-80^{0c}.

Some of the physical analysis including the moisture content, total ash content, Refractive index, specific gravity and pH were determined according to (AOAC, 2000). The determination of the water soluble ash, Alkalinity of soluble ash and acid insoluble ash were carried out according to (Pearson *et al.*, 1981). Chemical analyses including acid value, peroxide value, iodine value, saponification value were determined according to the (AOCS, 1988). For the iodine number determination, only freshly extracted oils which were subjected to minimum heat treatment were used. The Carotenoid content was determined according to (BSMA, 1977).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Results

Fig 1.0 illustrates the relative percentage values of the moisture, total ash, water soluble ash, acid insoluble ash and percentage yield of both samples. Table 1.0 below include results of the physical and chemical properties of the seed samples and extracted oil.

Fig 1.0: Physical parameters of White star Apple and Paw-paw seeds.

Table 1.0: Physico-chemical parameters of *Chrysophyllum albidum* and *Carica papaya* seed samples and oils.

PARAMETER	VALUES	
	WHITE STAR APPLE	PAW- PAW
Alkalinity of soluble ash	0.0003mol/dm ³	0.0004mol/dm ³
pH	4.37	7.20
Specific gravity	0.93kg/m ³	0.89kg/m ³
Melting point	50 ^{oc}	25 ^{oc}
Boiling point	240 ^{oc}	232 ^{oc}
Refractive index	1.4483	1.4636
Acid Value	5.61mg/KOH/g	15.85mg/KOH/g
Peroxide Value	1.75meq/kg	3.25meq/kg
Iodine Value	20.6/100g of sample	38/100g of sample
Saponification value	185meq/KOH/gram	157meq/KOH/gram
Carotenoid content	144.8mg/kg ppm	23.30mg/kg ppm

DISCUSSION

The moisture content of the seeds of the white star apple and paw-paw were 13.9% and 84.4% respectively. The obtained values for both seeds are relatively high when compared with 4.03% obtained for seeds of *Phoenix dactylifera* (Sadiq *et al.*, 2003). The high moisture content of the seeds was suggestive of its short shelf life and keeping quality. The total ash content which is an index of the level of the mineral content in most edible fruits was 2.82% and 8.16%. The values are higher than that reported for *Gretum Africana* seeds (1.2%) (Ekop, 2007), they compared favourably with those reported for *Colocynthis citrullus* (2.9%) (Obasi *et al.*, 2010) and *Solonom nirum* L. (8.05%) (Akubugwo *et al.*, 2007). The water soluble ash which was 1.2% and 4.2% were higher than 0.2% reported for soursop seeds (Onimawo, 2012) and lower than 7.5% reported for *Ocimum sanctum* L. (Sarang and Ameeta, 2013). The water soluble ash is used to detect the presence of water exhausted material.

The acid insoluble ash which indicates the amount of silica present in the seeds samples was 2.3% and 3.5%. They are higher than 0.997% reported for groundnut seeds (Satish and Shrivastava, 2009) and lower than 5.78% reported for *Linum usitatissimum* seeds (Ujjwala *et al.*, 2015). Alkalinity of soluble ash was 0.0003mol/dm³ and 0.0004mol/dm³. They are lower than 8.821 reported for *Arachis hypogaea* L. (Satish and Shrivastava, 2011). The alkalinity of soluble ash indicates the level of adulteration of the seeds with minerals.

The oil yields of the white star apple and Paw-paw seeds were 4% and 30% respectively. The values obtained for both seed oils is higher than 0.03% reported for seed oil of *Piliostigma thonningii*, an under exploited plant found in Nigeria (Jimoh and Oladiji, 2005) and lower than 43% reported for groundnut seed oil (Apata and Ologhobo, 1994). The percentage oil yield of the star apple may classify them as average yielding and the relatively high percentage of oil obtained for paw- paw seed oil may be considered economically attractive for industrial extraction. The pH values obtained were 4.37 and 7.20, is in close agreement to the values obtained for water melon 4.9 reported by (Egbuono *et al.*, 2015) and higher than 10.24 reported for corn oil (Tur'yan *et al.*, 1996). The Ph indicates the level of corrosiveness of the oil. The white star apple seed oil is slightly acidic while that of the paw-paw seed oil is neutral.

The specific gravity of 0.93 obtained for the white star apple seed oil and 0.89 for paw- paw seed oil implies that both oils are less dense than water. The obtained values are in agreement with the values 0.89-0.93 reported for edible oils (Odufoye, 1998). The melting point values obtained for both oils are 44^oc and 25^oc. They are higher than 13^oc obtained for dikanut seed oil (Etong *et al.*, 2014) and 35^oc obtained for soya bean oil (Hammond *et al.*, 2005). The values are within the range reported for selected Nigerian oil seed (34^oc - 72^oc), (Onyeike and Acheru, 2002). The white star apple oil may contain mostly long chain saturated fatty acids due to its high melting point. Short chain and higher unsaturated fatty acids have been attributed to the low melting point of oils.

The boiling point of both oils was 240^oc and 232^oc respectively. These values are higher than 230^oc obtained for Neem seed oil (Jessinta *et al.*, 2014) and lower than 299^oc obtained for olive oil (Ali *et al.*, 2013). The boiling point is a measure of the presence of saturated and unsaturated fatty acids in the oils. The higher boiling point of the white star apple seed oil means that it is rich in saturated fatty acids and has a denser structure than the paw-paw seed oil. The refractive indices for the two oils were 1.4483 and 1.4636. The values obtained do not differ much from the value reported for castor bean oil 1.47 (Kyari, 2008), falls within the range reported for some oils in the nut family 1.45-1.49 (Eckey, 1954). This means that the oil is not as thick compared to most drying oils whose refractive indices are between 1.48 and 1.49 (Duel, 1951).

The acid value which is an indicator of the edibility of the oil was 5.6mg/KOH/g and 15.85mg/KOH/g for both oils. These values are lower than 51.4mg/KOH/g reported for orange seed oils (Okoye and Ibeto, 2010). They are higher than the range 0.034-0.540mg/KOH/g reported for *S. Birrea*, *B. Sapida* and *B. Parkii* oils (Kyari, 2008). The acid value can also be used to check the level of oxidative deterioration of the oil by enzymatic or chemical oxidation. Peroxide value is the most common determinant of lipid oxidation. It measures the milliequivalents of oxygen per gram of oil. The peroxide values were 1.75meq/kg and 3.25meq/kg, respectively. These values falls within the range 0.39-7.4 reported for conventional seed oils in Nigeria and Congo Brazzaville (Akpambang *et al.*, 2008).

These values suggest that the oils are stable and may not readily become rancid during storage.

The iodine value is a measure of the unsaturation of oils, therefore, the values: 20.6gI₂/100g oil and 38gI₂/100g oil, do not suggest high unsaturation. These low iodine value for both oils indicates that the oil has a low content of unsaturated fatty acids which confirms these oils as non-drying oil. Saponification value of oil serves as an important parameter in determining the suitability of the oil for soap making (Akpabio *et al.*, 2011). Saponification value 185mg/KOH/gram and 157mg/KOH/gram obtained for both oils are higher than 132.3mg/KOH/gram reported for pumpkin seed oil (Younis *et al.*, 2000) and lower than 257 mg/KOH/ gram reported for coconut oil (Oshinowo, 1987). The high saponification value suggests the use of the oil in production of liquid soap, shampoos and lather shaving creams (Akbar *et al.*, 2009)

The carotenoid value obtained for both seed oils were 144.8mg/kg ppm and 23.30mg/kg ppm. These values were lower than 600mg/kg ppm reported for buriti oil (Ferreira de Franc *et al.*, 1999). The high level of carotene in the white star apple oil offers greater stability to the oil towards rancidity.

CONCLUSION

This study provides an insight on the physicochemical characteristics of the white star apple and paw paw seed oils. The data presented here suggests that these seeds may be used as supplementary sources of edible and industrial oil. It is felt that the present yields of these seeds can be markedly improved, by careful selection and breeding programmes. These seeds present examples of untapped food sources that have the potential of industrial adoption.

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